

POLAND

POLAND

THE PERSPECTIVE OF INTRODUCING A PROGRAMMATIC BUDGETING SYSTEM IN THE FIELDS OF HEALTH CARE AND EDUCATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Khushmuratov Zoyir Bektemirovich

Chief specialist of the State Budget Policy Department of the Ministry of
Economy and Finance, independent researcher of the Bank Finance Academy

Z_Xushmurotov@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11505612>

Financial-credit, budget and tax policies are conducted in the context of economic diversification, transformational economic relations, the specific social orientation of the transition to the market economy and the gradual implementation of reforms are chosen. Therefore, the implementation of fundamental economic reforms related to the formation of market relations in our country requires the improvement of the directions of the state financial-budget and tax policy.

Programme budgeting is one of such tasks, which creates opportunities for positive solutions to issues such as increasing the efficiency of state budget execution, achieving results of budget expenditures, further improving social protection of the population, improving budget relations in the stability of the country and ensuring their stability.

Program budgeting is a method of budget formation, and the budget formation process is based on the programs implemented within the budget. The program is a set of actions (measures) aimed at achieving specific results. Program-based budgeting requires the inclusion of program-related information in addition to detailed financial information.

The main goal of introducing programme budgeting is to increase the efficiency of public finance management. Increasing the efficiency of public spending requires further expansion of the scope of scientific research directly related to the improvement of the efficiency of public services.

The introduction of the software budgeting system, which is the most modern instrument, helps all participants of the budget process to join the process of making budget decisions and monitoring its implementation.

The goals, tasks and functions of the state, which is the main element of the political system of society, are revealed through the development and implementation of state policy.

Introducing a new "result-oriented budget" system of forming the annual budget in our republic is one of the important goals of the "2020-2024 strategy

for improving the public finance management system of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

Today, developed and developing countries need to introduce a programmatic budgeting system from the planned budget process in order to improve the efficiency of work on the development of the budget project and its implementation.

Programmatic budgeting is one of the performance-based budgeting models. Performance budgeting aims to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of public spending by linking the funding of public sector organizations to the results they achieve. The most basic form of performance-based budgeting is the form in which performance information is systematically used in the preparation of the general state budget.

By introducing a system of programmatic budgeting to the healthcare and education sectors, the efficiency and effectiveness of those allocated to this area will be increased, and a mechanism for evaluating their effectiveness will be created. By introducing the software budgeting system in the health and education sectors, the accountability to the Parliament will be increased in these directions. The introduction of the software budgeting system, which is the most modern instrument, is to involve all participants in the budget process in the process of making budget decisions and controlling its implementation. According to Decree No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023 on the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the introduction of the "Result-oriented budgeting" system is established. Today, developed and developing countries need to introduce a programmatic budgeting system from the planned budget process in order to improve the efficiency of work on the development of the budget project and its implementation..

Suggestions for improving the programmatic budgeting system: Strengthening the relationship between the strategic planning system and the budget planning, including revising the stages of the budget process as possible and harmonizing it with the beginning of the development of strategic plans;

Introduction of programmatic budgeting principles into the budget legislation (amendments to the Budget Code and other relevant documents);

Control of the effectiveness of the use of budget funds making, creating a base of indicators and their monitoring set up a mechanism.

References:

1. Decision No. 4 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the regulation on the procedure for developing, monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of budget programs of allocators of budget funds in

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

the implementation of the program budgeting system in the Republic of Uzbekistan"

2. Program Classification for Performance-Based Budgeting: How to Structure Budgets to Enable the Use of Evidence, https://ieg.worldbankgroup.org/sites/default/files/Data/reports/performance_based_budgeting_bb.pdf

3. I.A. Azizova Result-oriented budgeting. Tashkent - 2010.

4. G. Akhmedova "Efficiency-oriented budgeting is an important branch of medium-term planning"// Finance. 2010 year. Pages 26-29

5.A.Islamkulov "Improving the budget process by switching to the efficiency-oriented budgeting system"// Finance. 2010 year. Pages 4-12

6. I.V. Starodubrov "Result-oriented budgeting at the regional and municipal levels: approaches and recommendations", 2008. Pp. 9-26